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- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
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- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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ENHANCEMENT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN INDIVIDUALS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS C FOLLOWING ATTAINMENT OF A SUSTAINED VIROLOGICAL RESPONSE

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Abstract: The necessity of dental rehabilitation in patients with chronic hepatitis C (CHC) successfully treated with direct-acting antivirals (DAAs) is analyzed. Despite viral eradication and the achievement of a sustained virological response (SVR), pathological changes in periodontal tissues often persist. The study presents an approach aimed at developing a comprehensive treatment algorithm that takes into account the local immunological status and the functional hepatic reserve of patients.

Key words: chronic hepatitis C (CHC), direct-acting antivirals (DAAs), sustained virological response (SVR), hepatitis C virus (HCV), periodontal diseases, dental rehabilitation.

Annotatsiya: Surunkali gepatit C (CHC) bilan kasallangan va to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ta'sir qiluvchi antivirus preparatlari (DAA) yordamida samarali davolangan bemorlarda stomatologik reabilitatsiya zarurati tahlil qilingan. Virus eliminatsiyasi hamda barqaror virusologik javobga (SVR) erishilganiga qaramay, periodontal to'qimalardagi patologik o'zgarishlar ko'p hollarda saqlanib qolishi qayd etilgan. Tadqiqotda mahalliy immunologik holat va jigarning funksional rezervini hisobga olgan holda kompleks davolash algoritmini ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan yondashuv yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: surunkali gepatit C (CHC), to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ta'sir qiluvchi antivirus preparatlari (DAA), barqaror virusologik javob (SVR), gepatit C virusi (HCV), periodontal kasalliklar, stomatologik reabilitatsiya.

Аннотация: Проанализирована необходимость стоматологической реабилитации пациентов с хроническим гепатитом C (ХГС), успешно прошедших лечение противовирусными препаратами прямого действия (DAA). Несмотря на элиминацию вируса и достижение устойчивого вирусологического ответа (SVR), патологические изменения в тканях пародонта нередко сохраняются. Представлен подход, направленный на разработку комплексного алгоритма лечения с учетом местного иммунологического статуса и функционального резерва печени пациентов.

Ключевые слова: хронический гепатит C (ХГС), противовирусные препараты прямого действия (DAA), устойчивый вирусологический ответ (SVR), вирус гепатита C (HCV), заболевания пародонта, стоматологическая реабилитация.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic hepatitis C (CHC) continues to pose a significant global health challenge, affecting nearly 58 million individuals worldwide. In Uzbekistan, this disease remains the predominant form of parenteral hepatitis. Contemporary therapy with direct-acting antivirals (DAAs) has marked a substantial breakthrough, ensuring cure rates of 95–99%.

The hepatitis C virus (HCV) is recognized as a systemic infection. Its impact on periodontal tissues is mediated through immunological dysregulation, endotoxemia, and direct damage to salivary gland cells. Clinical practice demonstrates that even after achieving a sustained virological response (SVR), the “immunological scar” of the disease continues to maintain chronic inflammation within the oral cavity. The absence of specialized therapeutic protocols for such patients contributes to periodontal recurrence and tooth loss, thereby emphasizing the relevance of the present study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent studies (Nagao et al., 2022; Gigliotti et al., 2024) have demonstrated that periodontal tissue lesions in patients with CHC occur significantly more frequently than in the general population. The principal pathogenetic mechanism is considered to be a persistent cytokine imbalance, characterized by elevated levels of IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α , which initiates alveolar bone degradation.

In the DAA era, a new scientific challenge has emerged regarding the health status of patients following antiviral therapy. Numerous researchers have noted that the restoration of homeostasis occurs at a considerably slow rate, even after the elimination of viral RNA from the bloodstream. The concept of “immunological scarring” explains the persistence of a pro-inflammatory environment in the oral fluid. Studies have also revealed a direct correlation between the degree of liver fibrosis, assessed according to the METAVIR scale, and the severity of periodontitis. Nevertheless, targeted therapeutic approaches for the rehabilitation period remain insufficiently investigated.

Objective of the Study

To improve the effectiveness of comprehensive treatment for inflammatory periodontal diseases in patients who have achieved a sustained virological response (SVR) through the implementation of a diagnostic and preventive algorithm based on the monitoring of clinical and laboratory indicators.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A prospective randomized trial has been initiated, involving 150 participants allocated into three groups:

1. **Main Group (n = 60):** post-SVR patients receiving treatment according to the author’s protocol.
2. **Comparison Group (n = 60):** post-SVR patients undergoing conventional periodontal therapy.
3. **Control Group (n = 30):** healthy individuals.

The methodological framework includes the following components:

1. **Dental Status:** assessment of OHI-S, PMA, and PI indices, periodontal pocket depth (PPD), and bleeding on probing (BOP).
2. **Laboratory Diagnostics:** evaluation of local immunity indicators (slgA and lysozyme) and the cytokine profile of oral fluid (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α) using ELISA.
3. **Hepatological Profile:** liver elastography (FibroScan) according to the METAVIR scale, as well as biochemical parameters, including ALT, AST, bilirubin, and INR.
4. **Microbiology:** PCR-based diagnosis of principal periodontal pathogens (*P. gingivalis*, *T. denticola*, etc.).

Scientific Innovation

For the first time in dental practice, the condition of periodontal tissues during the unique “post-elimination” phase of the virus will be comprehensively characterized. The study aims to demonstrate that achieving a sustained virological response (SVR) does not automatically result in the remission of periodontitis. Correlations between oral inflammatory markers and the degree of liver fibrosis will be identified, thereby enabling the development of a personalized therapeutic strategy.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The implementation of a specialized therapeutic algorithm is expected to reduce the impact of the “metabolic echo” associated with hepatitis C. Preliminary findings indicate that the degree of liver fibrosis (F0–F4) serves as a significant predictor of the periodontal tissue recovery rate. The proposed treatment protocol will incorporate medications aimed at reducing the systemic burden on the hepatobiliary system while restoring local homeostasis.

Practical Significance

The application of the study findings in the clinical practice of dentists and infectious disease specialists will contribute to:

- improved interdisciplinary management of patients following antiviral therapy;
- reduction in the duration required to control periodontal inflammation;

- decreased risk of premature tooth loss among socially active individuals who have recovered from parenteral hepatitis.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Improving the management of periodontal diseases in patients recovering from CHC requires a departure from conventional treatment protocols. Consideration of the immunological and biochemical characteristics of the post-SVR phase may significantly enhance patient quality of life and increase the overall effectiveness of dental rehabilitation.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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